

John Winthrop describes the treatment of scurvy with lemon juice (1631)

by Harri Hemilä

James Lind is often credited with discovering or proving that citrus fruits are effective in preventing and treating scurvy. However, reports highlighting the benefits of oranges appeared more than two centuries before Lind's (1753) treatise. Oranges were already indicated for scurvy in accounts from Vasco da Gama's first voyage,¹ and similar suggestions were recorded by Ronsseus,² Hawkins,³ Pyrrard,⁴ Woodall,⁵ John Smith⁶ and many others before Lind's treatise.⁷ In his journal, John Winthrop described that when a ship supplied juice of lemons in 1631, many patients suffering from scurvy recovered rapidly. The relevant passage from his journal is reproduced in this document.

The extracted text section was cited in:

Nichols JB. Note on the history of scurvy.

Ann Med Hist. 1937;9(3):286-287.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7942891>

McCord CP. Scurvy as an occupational disease. XII. Scurvy in the early American Colonies.

J Occup Med. 1972;14(7):556-9. [p.559]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4556432>

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Tickner FJ, Medvei VC. Scurvy and the health of European crews in the Indian Ocean in the seventeenth century. Med Hist. 1958;2(1):36-46. [p.43]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/13515823>

Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

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<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Hemilä.

1 Scurvy during *Vasco da Gama's* first voyage (1497-1499).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17781205>

2 Description of scurvy by *Ronsseus* (1564).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093314>

3 Scurvy during *Richard Hawkins'* voyage (1593).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001137>

4 *François Pyrrard's* description of scurvy during a sea voyage (1602-1603).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18415628>

5 Description of scurvy symptoms by *John Woodall* (1617).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10651214>

6 *John Smith* recommended the use of lemon juice as a treatment for scurvy (1626).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18623985>

7 Baron JH. Sailors' scurvy before and after James Lind – a reassessment.

Nutr Rev. 2009;67(6):315-32. [p.317-318]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19519673>

John Winthrop, biographies

“John Winthrop was an English Puritan lawyer and a leading figure in the founding of the Massachusetts Bay Colony, the second major settlement in New England following Plymouth Colony. Winthrop led the first large wave of colonists from England in 1630 and served as governor for 12 of the colony’s first 20 years. His writings and vision of the colony as a Puritan ‘city upon a hill’⁸ dominated New England colonial development, influencing the governments and religions of neighboring colonies in addition to those of Massachusetts.”

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/John_Winthrop

[https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Author:John_Winthrop_\(1588-1649\)](https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Author:John_Winthrop_(1588-1649))

<https://www.britannica.com/biography/John-Winthrop-American-colonial-governor>

<https://doi.org/10.2307/2544439>

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1919049>

<https://doi.org/10.5224/masshistrevi.18.1.0001>

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<https://archive.org/details/winthroptsjournal00wint/page/2/mode/2up>

8 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/City_upon_a_Hill
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/A_Model_of_Christian_Charity
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<https://minio.la.utexas.edu/webeditor-files/coretexts/pdf/163020model20of20christian20charity.pdf>

WINTHROP'S JOURNAL
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VOLUME I

Section describing juice of lemons for scurvy:

1825, p.41-45

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<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=nyp.33433081782371&seq=67>

1853, p.49-54

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1908, p.57-58

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Introduction describing John Winthrop:

<https://archive.org/details/winthropsjournal00wint/page/20/mode/2up>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=inu.30000035059702&seq=19>

1631

January.] A house at Dorchester was burnt down.

February 11.] Mr. Freeman's house at Watertown was burned down, but, being in the daytime, his goods were saved.

Feb. 5.] The ship *Lyon*, Mr. William Peirce, master, arrived at Nantasket. She brought Mr. Williams,⁹ (a godly minister,) with his wife, Mr. Throgmorton, [blank] Perkins, [blank] Ong, and others, with their wives and children, about twenty passengers, and about two hundred tons of goods. She set sail from Bristol, December 1. She had a very tempestuous passage, yet, through God's mercy, all her people came safe, except Way his son, who fell from the spritsail yard in a tempest, and could not be recovered, though he kept in sight near a quarter of an hour. Her goods also came all in good condition.

Feb. 8.] The governor went aboard the *Lyon*, riding by Long Island.

Feb. 9.] The *Lyon* came to an anchor before Boston, where she rode very well, notwithstanding the great drift of ice.

Feb. 10.] The frost brake up; and after that, though we had many snows and sharp frost, yet they continued not, neither were the waters frozen up as before. It hath been observed, ever since this bay was planted by Englishmen, viz., seven years, that at this day the frost hath broken up every year.

The poorer sort of people (who lay long in tents, etc.) were much afflicted with the scurvy, and many died, especially at Boston and Charlestown; but when this ship came and brought store of juice of lemons, many recovered speedily. It hath been always observed here, that such as fell into discontent, and lingered after their former conditions in England, fell into the scurvy and died.

Feb. 18.] Capt. Welden, a hopeful young gentleman, and an experienced soldier, died at Charlestown of a consumption, and was buried at Boston with a military funeral.

9 Footnote in Winthrop's journal:

"Here enters upon our stage Roger Williams, one of the most illustrious and important characters concerned with early New England. During his life of eighty years (1603-1683) he affected the course of history in both the old and the new world ... "

Roger Williams:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Roger_Williams

<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Roger-Williams-American-religious-leader>

<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511921612.002>

Of the old planters, and such as came the year before, there were but two, (and those servants,) which had the **scurvy** in all the country. At Plymouth not any had it, no not of those, who came this year, whereof there were above sixty. **Whereas, at their first planting there, near the half of their people died of it...**